

**The impact of the co-production on the lived experience in a
"phygital" store: a value-based approach
Proposal of a model**

**L'impact de la co-production sur l'expérience vécue dans un
magasin " phygital " : une approche par la valeur.
Proposition d'un modèle**

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Abstract

The advent of new digital technologies seems to have changed people's consumption habits and decision-making processes. The marketing literature is full of discussions about the evolution of the customer experience over the last few decades, and the development of the status of the consumer. Indeed, the consumer has gone from being a rational consumer to an emotional consumer and finally to be considered a "prosumer".

In addition to becoming an emotionally driven being and seeking unique and extraordinary shopping experiences, the consumer wants to participate in the production of his or her in-store experience, thus being part of the value creation process of his or her own experience, which has become easy thanks to the digital tools present in the physical sales space.

This new form of commerce, called "phygital", represents a perfect combination of physical and virtual channels, and is now the most common retail strategy adopted by retailers worldwide. This new hybrid purchasing model is leading to changes both in the distribution channels used by retailers and in the way consumers behave.

The objective of this article is to propose a research model aiming at linking the co-production of experience and the experience lived by the consumer in a phygital sales space.

Keywords: consumer experience; lived experience; co-production; co-creation value; phygital.

Résumé

L'avènement des nouvelles technologies numériques semble avoir modifié les habitudes de consommation des individus et leurs processus de décision. La littérature marketing regorge de discussions sur l'évolution de l'expérience du client au cours des dernières décennies, et sur le développement du statut du consommateur. En effet, ce dernier est passé d'un consommateur rationnel à un consommateur émotionnel pour être finalement considéré comme un "prosumer".

En plus d'être devenu un être guidé d'abord par ses émotions et de rechercher des expériences d'achat uniques et extraordinaires, le consommateur désire participer à la production de son expérience en magasin, faisant ainsi partie du processus de la création de valeur de sa propre expérience, ce qui est devenu facile grâce aux outils numériques présents dans les espaces de vente physiques.

Cette nouvelle forme de commerce appelé le « phygital », représente une parfaite combinaison des canaux physiques et virtuels, et figure désormais comme la stratégie de distribution la plus fréquemment adoptée par les enseignes à l'international. Ce nouveau modèle d'achat hybride entraîne des changements aussi bien au niveau des canaux de distributions de la part des distributeurs qu'au niveau du comportement du consommateur.

L'objectif de cet article est de proposer un modèle de recherche visant à mettre en relation la co-production d'expérience et l'expérience vécue par le consommateur dans un espace de vente phygital.

Mots-clés : expérience de consommation ; expérience vécue ; co-production ; co-crédation de valeur ; phygital.

Introduction

Today's world is hyperconnected and over-informed, and the individual evolves in a context where immediacy prevails, where he is connected to everyone, everywhere, and at any time. Companies have understood this and are in the process of "solving the digital equation" or "carrying out their digital revolution". And it is in this light that we notice that the digitalization of retail impacts not only the exchanges, the actors, the offer but also the points of sale (Hagberg et al. 2016), innovation in retail triggers its competitiveness and growth (Pantano et al., 2017,2018).

Consumers, whose motivation to visit retail outlets is mainly hedonic, might consider the store as a place for socializing, discovering, walking, and relaxing (Filser, 2000), which highlights its recreational function. The visit to the store thus becomes itself a source of value for the individual; the consumption of the point of sale becomes more important than the products offered there (Filser, 2001). Moreover, the consumer has disengaged from his traditional function of consumption. He no longer wants to be perceived as a destroyer of goods, but rather wants to become the master and producer of his own experience. And this has become possible through digital transformation (Neuhofer et al., 2013; Payne et al., 2008).

In an era where the consumer is no longer considered a passive actor, a simple receiver of the product or service, but rather an active actor, co-actor of his own value (Vargo and Lusch, 2004), more and more demanding, competent, able to juggle between several resources offered at will (time, money, skills) (Arnould, 2005; 2007; Vargo and Lusch, 2004) in order to satisfy his needs, it has become imperative for companies to change their traditional strategy based on creating value in an isolated way. Involving consumers in the process of creating their own value is one of the best strategies for a company to better satisfy its customers through more personalized offers (Hoyer et al., 2010) and to strengthen its competitive advantage.

The process of value co-creation is migrating from a company and product-centric view to a more balanced view in which the company and the customer interact to create joint added value (Damkuvienė et al., 2012).

The presence of digital tools in stores is considered the keystone of the integrated shopping experience and digital experience (Blázquez, 2014), a phenomenon that is called "phygital"

that combines the physical space, the store and the digital, the Internet, a perfect combination of both forms of commerce (traditional and electronic). This new conception of the store, on the border between commerce and leisure, has led researchers and practitioners to propose the term "retailtainment" which emphasizes the playful and hedonistic character of the store visit.

Indeed, mobile digital technologies as a source of interactivity and connectivity enhance the customer's experience (Zhou and Lu, 2011), allowing him to better control it to make it his own (Saarijarvi et al., 2014), which has earned the consumer his new status of "prosumer" thereby modifying his relationship with the company (Laurent, 2008).

Through a literature review, we aim in this article to provide an answer to the following central question: what is the impact of the co-production on the experience lived by consumers in a "phygital" stores?

This article has a double interest; a theoretical interest which consists in proposing a conceptual framework defining the semantic borders between the phygital experience and the co-production of experiences while specifying their interaction links. It also has a managerial interest, as it aims to enlighten sales practitioners on the unconventional levers that have a positive impact on the lived experience.

Through the following paragraphs, we try to conceptualize the concepts of "co-production" and "lived experience in a phygital store" while highlighting the semantic boundaries between the two concepts. Then, we present our research model which puts in relation the dimensions "lived experience" and "co-production". We also expose the research hypotheses as well as our epistemological posture and methodological approach.

1. Conceptual framework

1.1.Experience

1.1.1. The consumer experience

The experiential approach, initiated by the founding work of Holbrook and Hirshman in 1982, focuses on understanding the individual's decision-making and consumption process. It advocates that the classical cognitive models postulating the rationality of the individual and his consumption neglect other dimensions, notably the emotional dimension. Holbrook and Hirshman's research (1982), highlighted the need to complete these traditional models by considering the experiential aspects of consumption.

Our literature review has enabled us to distinguish two interdependent fields of research. The first, which is part of the field of consumer behavior analysis, considers the consumer experience as a key concept in the theory of consumer culture (CCT) (Arnould and Thompson, 2005), and the second, from a more strategic perspective, sees it as the main foundation of an "experience economy" (Pine and Gilmore, 1999), which give birth to the experiential marketing (Schmitt, 1999), which is interested in the ways of creating extraordinary experiences that allow the organization to gain a competitive advantage in its relationship with its customers. Our work is in line with this research.

Although the consumer is seen as an emotional being seeking experiences (Maffesoli, 1990) that can be provided by person-object-situation interaction (Punj & Stewart, 1983), he or she has also been treated as a narcissistic and emotional human being who uses consumption to construct meaningful experiences (LaSalle & Britton, 2003; Pine & Gilmore, 2011).

One of the most important dimensions of consumption is hyperreality (Baudrillard, 1992), but ordinary and extraordinary experiences have most often been theorized as being within and outside the realm of everyday life respectively (Bhattacharjee & Mogilner, 2013). While there is a tendency among consumers to prefer an experience lived in an increasingly spectacular and extravagant context (Ritzer, 1999) in which they will be immersed (Hetzl, 2002), and it is indeed for this reason that there is an urgent need to revalue the most ordinary and everyday experiences (Carù and Cova 2006) and to broaden the realm of experience from the "extraordinary" to the "ordinary" (Carù & Cova 2002), This amounts to adopting the "extension of the domain of experience" to all sectors of consumption (Benavent and Evrard, 2002), hence our interest in the retail sector and the shopping experience.

However, in the experiential perspective (Benavent and Evrard, 2002; Filser, 2002), the consumer does not seek only to participate in experiences, however spectacular and extraordinary they may be, or to react to stimuli as a passive actor. He wants to be the designer and active producer (de Certeau, 1980) of his own consumption experiences, even the most hyperreal ones, which allows him to appropriate his daily life (Cova and Cova, 2001).

1.1.2. The shopping experience

➤ Definitions and approaches

In marketing, several concepts and definitions of experience have emerged, but there is no unanimity among researchers. We will base ourselves on the definition of Punj and Stewart, (1983) who conceptualized the experience as the person-object-situation interaction (POS).

The literature reveals two major approaches that conceptualize the shopping experience. The first is the classical behaviorist approach and the second is related to social psychology.

The classical behaviorist approach represented by (Mehrabian and Russel, 1974; Bitner, 1992; Donovan and Rossiter, 1982; Donovan et al., 1994) determines the shopping experience as simple affective reactions to the different stimuli of the point-of-sale environment (design, ambiance, social environment), which leads the consumer to adopt either approach or avoidance behavior.

According to the proponents of the second approach, the shopping experience is not simply a visit to a point of sale at a given moment, or a simple reaction to the stimuli of the environment, but it is an interactive and dynamic process during which the consumer certainly experiences immediate sensations during his reciprocal interaction with the environment, but totally appropriates this space in order to build his personal experience.

In fact, a shopping experience is defined as the interaction of an individual with a place of sale, an interaction synonymous with total appropriation, thus inciting the consumer to be involved on the emotional and affective levels, in a cognitive and rational way, physically or praxeologically, as well as spiritually (Gentile et al., 2007) and symbolically. These are the different dimensions of the shopping experience identified in the literature.

➤ Concept of appropriation

Several researchers have taken an interest in the concept of appropriation in the field of management sciences, more specifically in service marketing and distribution (Aubert-Gamet, 1996 and 1997; Bonnin, 2002; Cova and Cova, 2001, 2004; Ladwein, 2003; Petr, 2002).

Two approaches have been revealed by the works dealing with the subject-object relationship: a "top-down" approach and a "recursive" approach:

- The first approach finds its source in the praxeological dimension of appropriation, in the sense that it is constructed in action (physical and psychological), it is based

mainly on work in environmental psychology according to which appropriation manifests itself as the exercise of authority, control or physical and/or psychological power over a place whether it is performed individually or collectively (Prohansky, Ittelson and Rivlin, 1970),

- The second approach sees appropriation as a recursive action between the subject and the object, insofar as appropriation participates in the construction of the self. Any action carried out on an object will therefore have repercussions on the subject. Often in marketing, it has been noted that the appropriated object is defined as a medium of self-expression (Belk, 1988).

In social psychology of the environment, Fisher (1980) defines appropriation as the interpretation of "behaviors and actions that express concrete forms of acting and feeling and that allow a hold on places and on the production of cultural signs". Following his work, three types of practices of appropriation were put forward: the nesting, the marking and the exploration of the space ".

- **The nesting** according to Fischer (1983, p. 48) corresponds "to forms of installation which always refer more or less explicitly to the creation of a home, and which, by all kinds of artifices and arrangements, allow the individual to make his nest". Through the deployment of skills acquired from previous experiences, the consumer builds a multi-dimensional home: not just physical but also mental, emotional and spiritual.
- **The exploration** of space allows "to spot, to notice, to receive diverse information and thus to initiate the interpretation of the place" (Fischer, 1981, p. 93). The consumer will try to locate new products or services that will serve as anchor points allowing him to become aware of the nature of the experience he is confronted with.
- **Marking** corresponds "to the set of relations and behaviors through which the individual can inscribe a personal character in space" It is "a kind of symbolic boundary" (Fischer, 1983, p. 44). As the name implies, the consumer will mark and give a unique "personal" meaning to his or her experience, which he or she will have developed on the basis of his or her experiences, referents and resources. The creativity of the individual and his prior knowledge will play a very important role in this stage, allowing him to impregnate himself with this experience and give it a meaning that is specific to his person.

Following these three operations, the consumer finds himself in a situation of immersion, and appropriates his experience through the appropriation of the point of sale.

1.2. Phygital: Key element of the co-production of the experience

1.2.1. Digital transformation in a point of sale: The "Phygital"

The retail landscape is constantly changing as systems, processes, and information and communication technologies become increasingly connected (Daunt and Harris 2017; Dennis et al. 2014; Ferracuti et al. 2019). The digitalization of retailing impacts not only the exchanges, the actors, the offer but also the points of sale (Hagberg et al. 2016). Retailers now find themselves having to focus on new holistic innovation concepts that focus on consumer needs, while leveraging their position in the value chain (Paredes et al., 2018). The "engagement platforms" that represent spaces (online/off line) allow actors in this process to interact to create value, and exchange their resources (Ramaswamy and Ozcan, 2014). Whether it is a question of co-innovation or simply the co-production of a product, service or experience (Cova, 2008), upstream or downstream of the company's offer. The work of Leclercq et al, (2016) has highlighted the role of "engagement platforms" in the process of value co-creation.

It has been noticed that the technological advancement has had a considerable impact not only on the nature of the services offered but also on the manner of distribution of that service (Barnett & Scheetz, 2003). According to Aubrey & Judge (2012), physical retail outlets should be rethought on four fronts: experience, service, logistics and integration into an omni-channel system.

Over the past decade, traditional retailers have moved from multi-channel to cross-channel to omni-channel. These three concepts have often been confused given their proximity over time (Beck and Rygl, 2015). But to put it simply, the new omnichannel approach (Lemon and Verhoef, 2016) has replaced the well-established rule of multichannel management (Frazier, 1999).

Under multichannel distribution, each channel was intended for a specific customer segment. The channels were managed autonomously in "silos" alongside their historical channel while accentuating the perceived gaps between them and reducing their synergies to avoid the risks of cannibalization and of course to maximize profitability and increase customer loyalty (Kumar and Venkatesan et al., 2005, 2006, 2007).

Next comes cross-channel distribution, which encourages consumer creativity (de Certeau, 1990; Cova and Cova, 2009). The latter is put into practice through the availability and multiplicity of physical and digital tools at his disposal, allowing him to create a tailor-made and fluid experience (Collin-Lachaud and Vanheems, 2015).

This approach was born even before multichannel perished (Payne and Frow, 2004; Geyskens et al. 2002; Kumar et al. 2006). It has come to encourage the migration of customers from one channel to another and additional sales (Vanheems, 2009), which has the attraction of offering a "seamless" experience between the different real (physical) and virtual (digital) channels (Aubrey & Judge, 2012). The cross-channel journey therefore offers a unique system that exploits the natural complementarities of the different channels (Steinfeld et al., 1999; Schoenbachler and Gordon, 2002; Dholakia et al., 2005; Weltevreden, 2007), which is all the more noticeable given the characteristics of the ROPO phenomenon "Research Online, Purchase Offline".

With the advent of the smartphone, the cross-channel approach has lost its glory in the face of customers who have become more connected, mobile, demanding and ubiquitous (Badot and Lemoine, 2013; Juanedaayensa et al., 2016), giving way to omnichannel retailing, which is defined as "an integrated sales experience that blends the benefits of physical stores with the information-rich experience of online commerce" (Rigby, 2011)

This new strategy would "integrate all sales channels (Piotrowicz and Cuthbertson, 2014) simultaneously (Verhoef et al., 2015; Vanheems, 2015), in order to capture the attention of consumers, providing them with an "exciting" and "efficient" experience (Pantano and Naccarato, 2010), known to present no fragmentation during the experiential experience.

The omnichannel or Smart retailing approach is defined as one as "an interactive and connected retailing system that supports the seamless management of different touchpoints to personalize the customer experience (...) and optimize the performance of these touchpoints" (Roy et al. 2017). This is perfectly in line with Priporas et al, (2017) and Vrontis et al, (2017) who recognize that "extended self-service spaces" (Vanheems 2013) represent the only solution to be implemented to generate an omnichannel experience that is beneficial to both customers and retailers.

The insertion of these in-store digital tools, once equated with online-only commerce (Bodhani, 2012) offers "a huge opportunity... to reinvent the physical store" (Aubrey and

Judge, 2012) thereby enhancing the relational, hedonic and aesthetic aspects of the experience (Girish Punj, 2012) and the service at the point of sale (Newsom et al., 2009; Liljander et al., 2006).

For Pantano and Priporas (2016), the digital transformation offers a new configuration of the points of sale, allowing a direct link between physical and digital environment (Ingarao, 2013). These new digital technologies have become facilitating means for consumers to express themselves, share, interact with each other and with the company, and thus co-create value (Neuhofer et al., 2013; Saarijarvi et al., 2014; Abbes and Hallem, 2016).

Digital technologies are often seen as a means to support the new role of the consumer (Cova and Cova, 2009), who has now become an actor in his or her consumption (Firat and Dholakia, 2006) and a co-creator of value (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004; Lusch and Vargo, 2006).

The navigation of the consumer between physical and digital spaces could lead to a new consumer figure, called a smart shopper (Arnould and Thompson, 2005), a smart shopper (Schindler, 1989) and a creative consumer (de Certeau [1990 (1980)]; Cova and Cova, 2009), or a consumer-producer "prosumer" (Ritzer and Jurgenson, 2010; Toffler, 1980).

1.2.2. Co-production of the experience

Several names for co-production have been identified, depending on the degree of consumer participation.

Ramaswamy (2009) defines co-production as a process by which consumption experiences are jointly produced and developed by firms and end-customers, resulting in a new space where the value created is shared

The prosumer is thus considered to be a highly skilled consumer, able to juggle multiple resources (Arnould, 2005; 2007; Vargo and Lusch, 2004) in order to satisfy his or her needs. Several researchers have also demonstrated the prosumer's interest in opinion sharing, opinion generation, communication but also co-creation with companies (Cova and Cova, 2012; Djelassi and Decoopman, 2013; Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2000; 2004).

In this research, we propose to define the shopping experience as a POS interaction: "person x object x situation" (Punj and Stewart, 1983), generating meaning and emotions for the subject

who lives it (Filser, 2002). Caru and Cova (2007) identify three categories of P.O.S. interactions

- Company-driven experiences: experiences driven by companies, in which the consumer is immersed in hyper-real contexts, themed, and controlled by the company.
- Consumer-driven experiences: consumer-driven experiences that take place in environments that are not controlled by the company and allow the consumer a significant degree of autonomy.
- Co-driven experiences: experiences that are co-driven by the company and the consumer. The company provides the elements and conditions necessary to produce the experience, the consumer shapes and produces his own experience through his active participation. This article will focus on this third category.

Several works have emphasized that the process of co-production of experiences is favored more by digital technologies (Neuhofer et al., 2013; Payne et al., 2008). The use of these technologies seems to be essential to co-creation. For their part, Neuhofer et al. (2013) propose a matrix that classifies consumption experiences into four categories based on the intensity of technology and co-creation. They find that the intensity of co-creation and technology use result in enhanced experiences. The strongest value a company can offer its customers combines co-creation and technology (Neuhofer, Buhalis, & Ladkin, 2013) (see Figure1).

Figure 1: Experience typology matrix- Linking co-creation and technology

Source: (Neuhofer et al., 2013)

Previous research (Carton, 2007) shows three discriminating characteristics of co-production (see Table 1):

- The level of participation that determines the importance of the consumer's input in the co-production (temporal, physical, cognitive, material input...),
- The number of participants which differentiates between co-productions involving one, several or a mass of consumers,
- The space of freedom that the consumer has to undertake his contribution in the production, for example the assembly of a piece of furniture in kit leaves only very little freedom in the way of undertaking the assembly:

Table 1: Dimensions of the co-production of an experience

Source: (Carton, 2007)

1.3. Co-creation of experience value:

- *The customers perceived value of a co-creative experience with the company*

The value perceived by the customer has always been synonymous with price and quality. Although these initial reflections on perceived value based on economic theory and the concept of utility are relevant, they remain rather simplistic and do not capture all the explanatory attributes of consumer behavior (Sweeney and Soutar, 2001; Sanchez et al., 2006).

In a marketing context, it has been recognized that the consumer co-creates a personal experience with the company, a source of multiple values (Xie et al., 2008). In this sense, value is no longer limited to aspects related only to price and quality, but encompasses other functional, cognitive, and affective aspects. This multidimensional approach has been well developed in the literature with several classifications.

According to Xie et al (2008) and Dong et al (2008), the values of the co-creation experience represent the benefits that the consumer can acquire as a result of his or her participation in the process of creating part of the company's offer.

Several works in marketing have addressed and focused on the perceived values of the co-creation experience. According to Holbrook (1999), perceived values can be classified into three categories (see Table 2):

- **Intrinsic self-oriented values:** recreational, aesthetic-sensory, emotional, psychological, spiritual, escapist, and appropriative.
- **Extrinsic self-oriented values:** informational, optimization, learning, reassurance, and freedom
- **Extrinsic values oriented towards others:** social link with and outside the company.

Table 2: Classification of perceived value

Value Category	Perceived Values	Definition
Intrinsic self-directed values	Recreational value	Refers to the fun and entertainment generated by the use of the device
	The aesthetic-sensory value	Refers to the stimulation and pleasure of the senses: visual, gustatory, olfactory, tactile... aroused by the use of the co-creation device.
	The emotional value	Refers to the feelings and emotions aroused by the use of the device such as pleasure, joy and well-being
	The psychological value	Refers to the ease of use and understanding of the service offered.
	The spiritual value	Refers to the individual's beliefs about the quality of life of the person and the group (social well-being)
	The escape value	Goes beyond the feeling of well-being, pleasure and fun. It refers to a state of total immersion or even a state of flow.
	The appropriation value	Refers to the ability of the device to allow the client to appropriate the space to access the experience
Extrinsic values oriented towards the self	The value of freedom	Alludes to the feeling of control that the co-creation device provides.
	The informational value	Allows to satisfy the need for information and reduces the uncertainty regarding the purchase decision or certain elements such as price, calories,...
	The optimization value	Refers to the possibility for the customer to optimize his choice through the use of the device
	The learning value	Goes beyond the simple informational value of price or calories. It translates the knowledge accumulated by the customer from a culinary point of view and the different possible combinations of the proposed ingredients
	Reassurance value	Refers to the ability of the device to reassure the customer and generate a sense of trust.
	The convenience value	Refers to the perceived ease of use and practicality of the selection and ordering device by the user.
Extrinsic values oriented towards others	The value of the social link with and without the company	Refers to the ability of the device to generate interactions with the staff in contact (servers) as well as with other customers, including companions

Source: (Holbrook, 1999)

The work of Chan et al, (2010) chose to measure the economic and relational values of the co-creation experience and examine their impact on satisfaction. Yim et al, (2012), also mobilized the economic, relational, and recreational values and measured their impact on

satisfaction as well as the positive emotions that the customer and employee experience when co-creating a service together. Dong et al (2008) used and adapted the Meuter et al (2005) scale to measure the perceived values of co-creation.

Table 3 summarizes the main studies that have been conducted on the perceived value of a co-creation experience by the consumer.

Table 3: Major studies of the perceived value of the co-creation experience

Author	Values of co-creation of the experience
Dong et al., (2008)	Values of self-actualization, confidence in skills, joy and independence
Xie et al (2008)	Fun, belonging, accomplishment, relational, self-respect, excitement, interpersonal, personal
Merle et al., (2008)	Hedonic, creative achievement values
Chan et al (2010)	Economic, relational values
Yim et al., (2012)	Economic, relational, recreational values

Source: (Abbes et al, 2016)

2. Research model:

Our research is based on the work of Punj & Stewart (1983) who defined the consumer experience as the interaction of "person", "object" and "situation" and also on the work of Caru and Cova (2007) who complemented this SOP paradigm and proposed the category of Co-driven experiences. The company provides the elements and conditions necessary to produce the experience, the consumer shapes and produces his own experience from his active participation. Our research model is inspired by the social psychology approach. This approach advocates that the consumption or shopping experience is not simply a visit to a point of sale at a given moment, or a simple reaction to environmental stimuli, but an interaction between the individual and the point of sale. It is an interaction between the individual and the point of sale. This interaction results in a total appropriation, involving the consumer not only emotionally and affectively, but also cognitively, rationally, physically or praxeologically, and even spiritually (Gentile et al., 2007).

Based on social psychology and the research of Ladwein (2003), we can consider that the appropriation of a co-production offer maximizes the lived experience. This led us to incorporate ownership into our research model as a moderating variable. This model is derived from environmental psychology, which justifies our choice of two approaches to appropriation, namely top-down and recursive. We consider these two perspectives to be complementary rather than antagonistic in the sense that both deal with the subject-object relationship.

Based on the principle that consumers do not react to their environment in the same way, we have also integrated consumer motivations as a moderating variable. Figure 2 below represents our theoretical model

Figure 2: Theoretical research model

Source: Authors

3. Hypotheses

- H1. Co-production positively impacts the lived experience.
- H1.1. Freedom space positively impacts the intrinsic value.
- H1.2. Freedom space positively impacts the extrinsic value.
- H1.3. Level of participation positively impacts the intrinsic value.

- H1.4. Level of participation positively impacts the extrinsic value.
- H1.5. Number of consumers positively impacts the intrinsic value.
- H1.6. Number of consumers positively impacts the extrinsic value.
- H2. Consumer motivations positively impacts the lived experience.
- H2.1. Utilitarian motivations positively impacts the intrinsic value.
- H2.2. Utilitarian motivations positively impacts the extrinsic value.
- H2.3. Hedonic motivations positively impacts the intrinsic value.
- H2.3. Hedonic motivations positively impacts the extrinsic value.
- H3. Appropriation of the experiential context positively impacts the lived experience.
- H3.1. Control positively impacts the intrinsic value.
- H3.2. Control positively impacts the extrinsic value.
- H4. Consumer motivations moderate the impact of co-production on the lived experience.
- H5. Appropriation of the experiential context moderates the impact of co-production on the lived experience.

4. Epistemological and methodological framework of the research

To conduct this research, we consider it appropriate to proceed by an empirical research method that will allow us to produce the results of the experiments and observations, confirm and affirm the hypotheses, in order to validate the experimental model following this. Our research is therefore based on a positivist epistemological framework and a hypothetico-deductive approach. This epistemological choice will allow us to explain and clarify the causal relations between the variables of our model by accompanying theoretical rules.

The research model that we propose in this article is only a first reference model. It is necessary to carry out other works to complete and finalize it to come out at the end with a model suitable for testing.

Our article is interested in clarifying the variables that can impact the lived experience generated through the co-production between consumer and distributor in a phygital sales space.

In order to operationalize the final research model, hypotheses will be tested and we will proceed to the empirical validation. The latter is based on the choice of the point of sale, the sampling method as well as the different measurements of the study variables.

Conclusion

Traditional economic literature is based on the model that separates the producer from the consumer, considering that, while the producer creates value, the consumer damages and destroys it during its use. However, following the pioneering article by Holbrook and Hirschman (1982), a new marketing approach has emerged to complement the experiential perspective. Collaborative marketing defends the new role of the creative consumer, co-actor of his value and co-producer of his experience.

On a theoretical level, we have shown the impact of the co-production of experiences on the lived experience, and the primordial role of the appropriation of the experiential context in this process.

If the intersection of the literature that has dealt with the cross-channel or multi-channel journey according to the cognitive paradigm of information processing and problem solving (Balasubramanian et al., 2005 ; Belvaux, 2004), and the experiential paradigm (Holbrook and Hirschman, 1982) has allowed a better understanding of the experience in a physical or virtual space, on the other hand - to our knowledge - very little work has been done concerning the omni-channel journey combining the concept of co-production of experience.

Troye and Supphellen (2012) demonstrated that individuals who engage in co-production positively bias their evaluation of an outcome and an input product. Therefore, participation in a mental or physical experiential consumption practice should positively affect experience evaluation.

In light of this, future work should focus more closely on the role of technologies, and more specifically SSTs (Self-Service Technologies), on the co-production of experiences and the evaluation of the consumer's experience.

This on the one hand, and on the other hand, we will have to determine the impact of co-production on the lived experience while including the different variables likely to moderate the relationship, analyze and study the role of the phygital experiential context in the appropriation process and motivations (utilitarian and hedonic) in order to develop measurement tools that will allow us to measure the impact of the co-production of experiences on the lived experience in a phygital point of sales.

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